

EBFMC25-OP-36 · Clinical and Sociodemographic Characteristics of Patients with Subjective Cognitive Impairment

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Subjective cognitive impairment is a clinical condition where there is a decline in memory and intellectual functions but not in neuropsychological tests and functionality. In previous studies, it was shown that subjective cognitive impairment may be an early sign of dementia.

Materials and Methods: In this study we reviewed data from 129 patients who presented to our neurology outpatient clinics with forgetfulness between 01.07.2023 and 01.03.2025 and were diagnosed with subjective cognitive impairment by excluding dementia, Alzheimer's disease or mild cognitive impairment. All patients were assessed using MMSE (Mini-Mental State Examination); Lawton & Brody Activities of Daily Living (ADL) scale; Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS); and Epworth Sleepiness Scale; in addition, age, smoking and alcohol use, comorbid vascular disorders, and presence or absence of hearing problems were also assessed.

Results: Mean age was 68.07 ± 7.31 years (min: 51, max: 89 years). Of the patients, 65 were female. It was found that mean MMT score was 27 while mean Lawton & Brody ADL score was 7. Based on GDS results; 42 patients were diagnosed with definitive depression while there was hearing problems in 28 patients. It was found that majority of patients (58%) had hypertension while 34% had diabetes mellitus.

Conclusion: The detailed evaluation of patients presented with forgetfulness, early diagnosis of the entity with masked clinical signs such as subjective cognitive impairment, meticulous follow-up, implementing measures needed and treatment are highly important regarding quality of life in these patients.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Cognitive loss, dementia, early diagnosis, subjective cognitive impairment

INTRODUCTION

Subjective cognitive impairment is a clinical condition where there is a decline in memory and intellectual functions but not in neuropsychological tests and functionality. It has been shown that subjective cognitive impairment may be an early sign of mild cognitive impairment and dementia (Mitchell et al., 2014). Today,

forgetfulness is a highly common complaint with higher likelihood among individuals older than 65 years. The studies on subjective cognitive impairment were generally conducted in individuals at advanced age, reporting that its incidence ranged from 32% to 88% among individuals older than 65 years (Bassett & Folstein, 1993; Cheng et al., 2023). In our study, we aimed to present data analysis of sociodemographic, clinical and selected risk factors in patients who were followed with a diagnosis of subjective cognitive impairment in our clinic.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study included 129 patients who presented to our neurology outpatient clinics with forgetfulness between 01.07.2023 and 01.03.2025 and were diagnosed with subjective cognitive impairment but not dementia, Alzheimer's disease or mild cognitive impairment. In all patients, cognitive state was assessed using MMSE (Mini-Mental State Examination), while instrumental daily living activities using Lawton & Brody Activities of Daily Living (ADL) scale; depression using Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS); and daytime sleepiness using Epworth Sleepiness Scale. In addition, vascular risk factors including hypertension, diabetes mellitus, dyslipidemia and history of cardiovascular disorder; smoking and alcohol use; presence or absence of hearing problems; age, gender and level of education were also assessed.

RESULTS

Mean age was 68.07 ± 7.31 years (min: 51, max: 89 years). Of the patients, %36.4 (n=47) were male whereas 64.6% (n=82) were female. In addition, 82.1% (n=106) were primary school graduate or illiterate while 15.6% (n=20) were secondary school or high school graduate and 2.3% (n=3) had college degree. It was found that mean MMT score was 26.75 ± 1.65 while mean Lawton & Brody ADL score was 7.34 ± 0.94 . Based on GDS results, it was found that there was definitive depression in 32.5% (n=42), possible depression in 10.8% (n=14) and no depression in 56.5% (n=73). Based on Epworth Sleepiness Scale results, it was found that 53.4% (n=69) of patients were normal while there was normal but increased dozing in 24% (n=31), increased but mild dozing 10% (n=13), increased moderate dozing 7.7% (n=10), increased severe dozing 4.6% (n=6). Of the patients, 21.7% (n=28) had hearing problem; 6.9% (n=9) were using hearing aids. Of the patients, 17.8% (n=23) were active smokers while 10.8% (n=14) quitted smoker and alcohol and 24.0% (n=31) were ex-smoker. In addition, it was reported that there was hypertension in 58.1% (n=75), diabetes mellitus in 34.1% (n=44), dyslipidemia in 9.3% (n=12), heart diseases in 13.1% (n=17), other comorbid disease in 58.9% (n=76) while there was no comorbid disease in 8.5% (n=11) of the patients.

DISCUSSION

The cognitive performance in subjective cognitive impairment hasn't been impaired as much as mild cognitive impairment. The subjective cognitive impairment differs from mild cognitive impairment and dementia by lack of abnormalities in neuropsychological tests and unaffected daily living activities. Individuals who performed normal in neuropsychological test despite memory complaints are defined as subjective cognitive impairment while individuals who performed 1.5 or 2 SD below normal score are defined as mild cognitive impairment (Abdulrab & Heun, 2008; Viviano et al., 2019). As a part of healthy aging, individuals experience performance loss in cognitive functions in advanced ages. In individuals at advanced ages, it is important whether cognitive disorders is a part of normal aging or transition to dementias together with subjective cognitive impairment. In a previous study, it was shown that there was complaints of memory in 15% of individuals aged 18 - 44 years, 43% of those aged 65 - 74 years, 51% of those aged 75 - 84 years and 88% of those 85 years or older and that the rate of increase was higher after 65 years of age and involved distinct cognitive function domains (Bassett & Folstein, 1993). In our study, mean age was 68 years in 129 patients, ranging from 51 to 89 years.

When assessed by gender, it was shown that mild cognitive function was more common in women, and it was suggested that cognitive impairment is associated to mood in women while it had objective association in men (Tomita et al., 2014). In our study, there was 82 of patients (64.6%) were female. As similar to dementias, lower educational level is also a risk factor for subjective cognitive disorder. In a study from South Korea, it was found that mean duration of education was 3.3 years in patients diagnosed with subjective cognitive impairment while it was 5.6 years in those without (Kim, Chang, Lee, & Bae, 2020). In a study from Turkey, Açıkgöz et al. linked low educational level to higher complaints of memory at advanced ages (Açıkgöz et al., 2014). In our study, majority of our patients (82.1%; n=106) were primary school graduate or illiterate while

15.6% (n=20) were secondary school or high school graduate and 2.3% (n=3) had college degree. In agreement with other studies, illiterate individuals or those with lower educational level comprised majority of our study population. Since the use of cognitive screening tests in subjective cognitive impairment (SCI) is not consistent with the definition and diagnostic criteria of the disorder, it is deemed that the use of cognitive screening tests such as the MMSE (Mini-Mental State Examination), which are used to detect the diagnosis and progression of Alzheimer's, other types of dementia, or mild cognitive impairment, are not suitable for routine practice (Jessen et al., 2014). However, in the studies, it was seen that the individuals with subjective cognitive impairment tended to perform worse on the MMSE compared to those without (Açikgöz et al., 2014). Thus, it seems that there is need for more comprehensive neuropsychological tests tailored to the nature of the disease. In our patients, the mean MMSE score was found as 27 in agreement with the literature. Subjective cognitive decline represents memory complaints due to forgetfulness in daily living activities (Açikgöz et al., 2014). In elderly individuals, the performance was assessed using the Lawton and Brody Instrumental Activities of Daily Living Scale in our study and found that there was no dependency in our patients with a score of 7.3 (Lawton & Brody, 1969). It is known there are also cognitive symptoms, in addition to emotional and physical symptoms in patients with depression. Subjective cognitive impairment is frequently seen in this patient group (Lahr et al., 2007; Ottowitz et al., 2002). In these patients, it is thought that the cognitive impairment in results from hippocampal damage and shrinkage, increased cortisol levels, and disruption of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis (Hammar & Årdal, 2009). In our patient population, it was found that there was definitive depression in 32.5% (n=42), possible depression in 10.8% (n=14) and no depression in 56.5% (n=73) based on GDS results. The studies suggest that hearing loss may be associated with dementia. The decreased stimulant effect due to hearing loss and consequent decline in social interaction also affects cognitive functions in an individual. When compared to those without hearing loss, patients the risk for dementia was increased by 2-folds in patients with mild hearing loss, 3-folds in patients with moderate hearing loss, and 5-folds in patients with severe hearing loss (Arlinger, 2003; Lin et al., 2011; Uhlmann et al., 1989). In our study population, 21.7% of patients (n=28) had hearing problem; 6.9% (n=9) were using hearing aids. Attention deficit is seen in patients with sleep disorders and excessive daytime sleepiness. As a result, decline in cognitive functions and memory problems develop. The risk for cognitive decline is increased by 30% in individuals with sleep disorders and it is recommended to follow such patients for dementia risk. In our study, it was found that 53.4% (n=69) of patients were normal while there was normal but increased dozing in 24% (n=31), increased but mild dozing 10% (n=13), increased moderate dozing 7.7% (n=10), increased severe dozing 4.6% (n=6) based on Epworth Sleepiness Scale results. It is thought that the shared vascular risk factors the possible reason underlying the relationship between subjective cognitive impairment and risk for stroke. In some studies, it was shown that there is a relationship between subjective cognitive impairment and micro-hemorrhage and white matter lesions (Cordonnier et al., 2006; Rostamian et al., 2014; Stewart et al., 2011). Thus, we evaluated the most common vascular risk factors including hypertension, diabetes mellitus, dyslipidemia, heart disease, smoking and alcohol use. It was found that there was hypertension in 58.1% (n=75), diabetes mellitus in 34.1% (n=44), dyslipidemia in 9.3% (n=12), heart diseases in 13.1% (n=17) of our patients while 17.8% (n=23) were active smokers while 10.8% (n=14) quitted smoker and alcohol and 24.0% (n=31) were ex-smoker.

CONCLUSION

The risk for development of dementia is 2-folds higher in elder individuals with subjective cognitive impairment when compared normal elderly population. Of the elder individuals with subjective cognitive impairment, 2.3% and 6.6% progress to dementias and mild cognitive impairment, respectively (Mitchell et al., 2014). It was shown that 10% of subjective cognitive impairment incidents may progress into dementia and mild cognitive impairment. It is recommended to assess subjective cognitive impairment in detail in patients who presented with forgetfulness but not received diagnosis of mild cognitive impairment or dementia (Moret-Tatay et al., 2023; Poptsi et al., 2023). The studies directed to early diagnosis and prevention of subjective cognitive impairment will help decreasing socioeconomic burden due to dementia.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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